

The Alan Turing Institute

A background image showing a close-up, slightly blurred view of laboratory equipment, including two metal pipette tips and several clear plastic microcentrifuge tubes. The image is partially obscured by a white diagonal shape on the left side.

Data Study Group Final Report: MRC Clinical Trials Unit, UCL

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Monitoring in clinical trials: Identifying
poor performance at recruitment sites
participating in clinical trial research

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Contents

1	Executive summary	2
1.1	Challenge overview	2
1.2	Data overview	2
1.3	Main objectives	3
1.4	Approach	4
1.5	Main conclusions	4
1.6	Limitations	5
1.7	Recommendations and future work	6
2	Introduction	6
2.1	Classifying site performance	8
2.2	Identifying features integral to site performance	8
2.3	Identifying new features	9
3	Data overview	9
3.1	Dataset description	9
3.2	Data issues	13
3.3	Exploratory data analysis	13
4	Experiments	15
4.1	Text-based Models	18
4.2	Numerical Methods	27
5	Future work and research avenues	34
5.1	Suggestions for Improvements to Available Datasets	35
5.2	Summary	36
6	Team members	37
6.1	Participants	37
6.2	Principal Investigator	38
6.3	Challenge Owners	39
6.4	Project Team	39
7	Funding	40
8	References	40

1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

This Data Study Group (DSG) Challenge aimed to build a human-in-the-loop machine learning model that could assist the Medical Research Council Clinical Trials Unit (MRC CTU) at University College London, in identifying clinical trial sites that are performing poorly and require monitoring intervention. When running clinical trials, patient safety is the greatest priority, with robust operation a secondary but nevertheless key feature in ensuring successful outcome of the trial. Poor performance therefore relates to any trial conduct that could compromise safety or lead to variation in how a trial is conducted between sites, making monitoring trials a large and complex challenge.

The CTU is responsible for ensuring that all clinical trial sites gather quality data, while also protecting patient rights and well-being. Currently risk-based monitoring is used to evaluate whether individual sites are following trial protocol. This approach relies on pre-defined metrics, such as those measuring the correct and timely completion of trial forms, as indicators of site performance and uses a trigger system based on those indicators to alert the CTU when a site visit is considered necessary. However, a recent study found that the intuitively developed pre-defined metrics were not sufficient at discriminating sites requiring a site visit, where relevant features may have been missed.

The purpose of this DSG challenge was therefore to undertake an initial investigation into whether machine learning approaches can improve identification of poorly performing sites.

1.2 Data overview

Four key sources of data were available as described in Table 1: 1) Case Report Forms (CRFs): routine forms completed for each patient during the course of the trial, with mixed response types (e.g. drop down box or text based), from which, 2) the current risk-based pre-visit assessment indicator metrics for each site ('trigger' values) are calculated. 3) monitoring reports from previously-visited sites: detailing all issues found

at the site, with assigned severity grade ('Critical', 'Major' or 'Other') and free-text comments for each issue, from which: 4) the ground truth values reflecting post-visit performance were calculated, with each site classified into one of three classifications (0 = no visit required, 1 = not usually visited, 2 = visit recommended), based on the number of issues found at the site and the severity level of the issues.

Name	Description
Case Report Forms (CRFs)	Routine forms completed for each patient during the course of the trial, with mixed response types (e.g. drop down box, numerical or text based)
Pre-defined trigger metrics	Risk-based pre-visit assessment indicator metrics for each site ('trigger' values) currently used by the monitoring team
Monitoring Reports	Detailing all issues found at previously-visited sites, with assigned severity grade ('Critical', 'Major' or 'Other') and free-text comments describing each issue
Post Visit Performance Class	Ground truth values reflecting post-visit performance, with each site classified into one of three classifications (0 = no visit required, 1 = not usually visited, 2 = visit recommended), based on the number of issues found at the site monitoring visit and the severity level of each of the issues found

Table 1: Summary of data available by type

1.3 Main objectives

The DSG challenge objectives were two-fold. The first was to investigate both current trigger metrics (and their associated thresholds) and possible new metrics, such that when combined, offered improved detection of poor performance that can better highlight which sites should be prioritised for in-person monitoring review. The second, to investigate whether machine learning models can be employed to improve detection of poor site performance.

There were three key considerations:

- * All models should reflect the priority of patient safety
- * Site monitoring visits are time consuming. With the limited capacity of the monitoring team, efficient selection of sites would be aided by the

implementation of a graded indicator of performance.

* Solutions should follow a white-box, transparent approach, with clear explanation on how the model reaches a classification, where monitoring teams are provided information on which factors influenced the classification outcome for each site. This would also allow monitoring teams to target specific areas of under-performance during monitoring visits.

1.4 Approach

In order to assess the performance of the triggers currently used for the trial by the CTU to identify poorly performing sites, exploratory data analysis was performed to examine relationships between current triggers and the ground-truth site classification labels (see Table 1).

Following data exploration and literature review, five numerical classification model types were selected to investigate their potential to classify sites using trigger data as inputs: logistic regression, support vector machines, random forest, XGBoost, and neural networks. Text-based approaches were also employed to investigate the monitoring issues found at sites, as detailed within the monitoring reports, with a view to making recommendations for improved trigger metrics.

1.5 Main conclusions

Exploratory data analysis revealed that the triggers that are currently used do not reliably predict which clinical trial sites are performing poorly and would therefore benefit from a monitoring visit. Numerical model site performance classification based on existing triggers demonstrated reasonable performance with two techniques: XGBoost (69% accuracy) and Random Forest (79% accuracy, an improvement of 43% over logistic regression, the worst performing model), indicating potential for improving discrimination of poorly performing sites over currently used techniques.

Searching for common issues in monitoring data using text-based approaches revealed potential avenues for new trigger metric development, with a key area highlighted by thematic analysis, LDA, word

clouds and the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes classifier of a lack of, or incomplete, documentation of patient consent. Whilst the current pre-visit trigger metrics include a simple measure relating to return of consent forms, expanding to include more complex aspects of form completion, such as ensuring that the process is undertaken by trained and approved staff, appears worthwhile.

1.6 Limitations

Due to the novelty of the project, the work undertaken during the DSG was intended as purely exploratory. Literature regarding the use of quantitative techniques for clinical trial monitoring is limited, especially regarding the implementation of machine learning techniques. Data available were also highly dimensional and complex, for example the CRFs contain over 2,000 questions collected on over 60 forms, with the majority of forms evolving over time, where questions within forms or entire forms may be added or removed, during the course of a trial. Furthermore, as is typical of clinical datasets, the data were incomplete.

Whilst a large dataset was available at patient level, at clinical trial site level, the data was of low sample size, with just 10 sites per class in the dataset used to build models during the challenge, which limited the accuracy that could be achieved in the numerical classification models built. A larger dataset would allow capture of more of the complex relationship between indicator variables and also have allowed clearer conclusions to be drawn regarding the utility of the current pre-visit triggers.

The monitoring reports contained high severity grading imbalance for the different performance issues found at trial sites, with many more 'Other' graded issues than either 'Major' or 'Critical' (up to a ratio of 325:1). Commenting style of different members of the monitoring team also varied widely. The exploration and analyses were therefore limited by the unique structures of the four datasets, the complex relationships between the data types and the limited time available for the challenge.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

Firstly, the use of text-based approaches to assess and automatically classify the detail within the monitoring reports should be refined and linked back to existing CRFs, to enable automatic extraction of new potential triggers. These new triggers can then be added as further feature inputs for the numerical classification models that were developed during the DSG to classify site performance. Model performance accuracy (with the additional feature inputs) can then be compared to the performance accuracy achieved with current trigger inputs, as described in this report.

It is suggested that this process be repeated on a trial-by-trial basis to allow trial specific models to be developed in the future. An initial larger, balanced, more structured dataset would enable a base system to be created, from which adapted systems can then be developed for each clinical trial, where for each different trial, early stage monitoring data can be used to refine the base system and effectively weight monitoring triggers to reflect their importance in determining site performance for that particular trial.

2 Introduction

Clinical trials are the gold-standard for assessing the efficacy and safety associated with new treatments. Such trials commonly compare a treatment versus standard care in a Randomised Control Trial (RCT), whereby the only difference between groups of patients is the received treatment. To ensure the rights, well-being, and safety of participants are protected, and research data are of high-quality and reliable, all clinical research must be compliant with guidelines presented by the International Conference on Harmonisation¹. All personnel involved in conducting clinical trials are trained in the proper conduct of running clinical trials using the Good Clinical Practice (GCP) framework².

Large scale, multi-site clinical trials are often monitored by a central

¹<https://ichgcp.net/>

²<https://www.nihr.ac.uk/health-and-care-professionals/learning-and-support/good-clinical-practice.htm>

Clinical Trials Unit (CTU), who oversee the entire trial and conduct regular checks on each of the sites taking part in the trial. It is the responsibility of the CTU to monitor site performance, visit sites where necessary and oversee required changes in trial conduct at sites not adequately adhering to GCP or trial protocols. On-site monitoring is highly recommended by ICH (section 5.18.3) through source-data verification (SDV), where case reports are verified against source notes. This is however highly resource-intensive, inefficient, and costly (Eisenstein et al. 2008; Funning et al., 2009; Lindblad et al., 2014). Therefore the development of improved automated monitoring techniques that allow the process to become more cost-effective, such as those based on machine learning techniques, are in great demand.

Risk-based monitoring is a now commonly used clinical approach, developed to try to address this issue and target poorly performing sites more effectively. Using this technique, sites are suggested for a monitoring visit if they breach performance indicators, or 'triggers'; for example a 'trigger' might be set regarding incomplete consent forms, which fires if greater than 5% of consent forms are incomplete. This approach has been supported (by both those conducting trials and regulators) and has potential for more efficient trial monitoring for both increased patient safety and ensuring trial conduct follows trial protocols (Beever et al., 2019; Tantsyura et al., 2015; Macefield et al., 2013).

Such approaches have however, shown limited value thus far. A recent review found that whilst most UK CTUs now employ risk-based monitoring, few provided systematic evidence that the triggers were effective (Beever et al., 2019), where triggers employed tend to be intuitively defined rather than empirically developed. A recent study (the 'TEMPER' study) compared matched triggered and untriggered sites, where the triggers (and their thresholds) had been guided by clinical intuition (Stenning et al., 2018). When monitoring visits were conducted, the study found no significant differences in the number of previously undiscovered serious issues (graded 'Major' or 'Critical') between matched groups of triggered and untriggered sites. Further, for both groups of sites, the number of new issues found was higher than expected. This suggests that for the clinical trials included in the study, the triggers used were not sufficiently discriminative in discerning whether a site required a monitoring visit.

The following sections operationalize the presented problem space and outline the key research questions this challenge addressed. This section further introduces the problem and the need to explore new discriminatory features. Section 3 describes the data in detail and the exploratory data analysis conducted. The text based and numerical models built are then described in section 4, with a summary of findings and suggestions for future work described in section 5.

2.1 Classifying site performance

Given that in-person monitoring is such a time-consuming process and is currently not well stratified, automated techniques that can identify sites where severe issues would likely be found (should a visit be conducted), allowing those sites to be prioritised for monitoring visits, are greatly in demand. Delays in visiting such sites may lead to exposure of participants to unnecessary health risks and may also result in poorer outcomes from the trial, for example through incorrect or missing data records. Therefore, the initial task for the DSG was to build a classifier which, given an input of site-specific information, such as pre-visit trigger data, could predict a performance class label for the site, indicating the number of severe issues that would be found, should a visit be conducted.

Performance classes were developed from the monitoring data ahead of the DSG. Three classes of performance were defined, in increasing severity, as 0 - no visit required, 1 - not usually visited or 2 - visit recommended. These were defined with the benefit of hindsight using the issues recorded from the site monitoring visit, with the (typically multiple) issues found at each site during the visit being combined into a single performance value for each site. With this ground truth, the numerical models created during the challenge could then learn from patterns in pre-visit data that were common across sites within each of the three different levels of performance.

2.2 Identifying features integral to site performance

Whilst development of such numerical models would be useful, it is also important to understand the specific reasons why a site is not performing well. To do this, interrogation of the numerical models is also necessary,

to understand and feed back to the monitoring team the particular signals in pre-visit data that reflect poor performance.

The primary measures currently used to determine need for site visit are the pre-visit trigger metrics, which cover different areas of trial conduct, such as data return or version control in the forms used, as described in detail in section 3.1. A secondary aim was therefore to investigate these different measures with a view to feeding back which of the measures are most useful in determining performance classification.

2.3 Identifying new features

Further to the above, the recent TEMPER study demonstrated that when the currently used triggers are used to identify poorly performing sites (based simply on the number of triggers that fired), they were little better than chance at selecting which of the sites would most benefit from a monitoring visit. Whilst a machine learning model may be able to provide improved discrimination with the same data, the findings of the TEMPER study suggest that the currently used metrics are limited and that the development of additional trigger metrics may improve identification of poorly performing sites.

Therefore a third aim was to explore data at a participant (or patient) level, through the wealth of Case Report forms supplied, to investigate whether any further quantitative value could be exploited from this data, for example if common issues arose that were currently not measured as a pre-visit trigger metric.

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

For this challenge, four key sources of information were provided: 1) Case Report Forms (CRFs), 2) pre-visit trigger metrics, 3) Monitoring Reports and 4) post-visit performance classification as described in Table 1.

Each of these sources provided unique information for the challenge, and are described in more detail below. Data of these four types were

supplied from two separate studies. The first from a recent large-scale trial overseen by the CTU, (referred to as the 'main' study within this report). The second from the TEMPER study, as described above, in which 15 sites with trigger metrics indicating the requirement of a visit ('triggered') and 15 matched sites with trigger metrics indicating no requirement of a visit ('untriggered') were all assessed through monitoring site visits. As the latter study included some data from the 'main' study, data cannot be considered independent between the two studies.

Case Report Forms (CRFs)

The Case Report forms are forms completed by research staff at each trial site to record events within the trial, for each participant. The forms are completed at different timepoints during the trial (e.g. baseline, follow up, blood reports, serious adverse event reporting) and returned to the CTU. The pre-visit trigger metrics currently used to determine whether a site requires a monitoring visit are calculated from the CRFs.

CRF datasets were extracted in monthly batches, from October 2013 to November 2015 and from July 2018 to February 2020 (to coincide with the TEMPER and main study trigger and monitoring data respectively), providing a total of 46 separate timepoints. With each timepoint split into eight separate csv files, a total of 368 csv files and one text file with header detail were supplied. Each file consisted of 13 columns: SiteID, PatientID, Visit, Visit Cycle, Form, Form Cycle, Question, Question Name, Question Cycle, Response Code, Response, Response Date and Response Status.

This data contains responses to over 2,000 questions on 61 forms, with the forms evolving over the course of the study. With over 11,000 recruited patients, 61 different forms being used within the trial and multiple responses within each form, in excess of 418 million rows of data were supplied. These rows of data consisted of a mixture of numeric, date, drop-down categorical, yes/no, tick-box, and free-text response types across different questions. These data therefore represent an incredibly complex dataset to analyse.

Pre-Visit Trigger Metrics

Pre-visit trigger metrics, calculated from Case Report Form data, are

calculated and reviewed approximately every three months by the monitoring committee. If two or more of the metrics (listed below) fire, i.e. a threshold has been met for the site, the monitoring committee discuss whether a monitoring visit is deemed necessary, considering both the site's trigger metrics and other factors such as recent responsiveness to email and any known temporary issues at the site, such as limitations in staffing that could have led to a temporary, explainable reduction in performance. Data for each of these triggers for each site was supplied for the DSG, matching the time periods described above.

Whilst trigger metrics were supplied for both the main and TEMPER datasets, as the experimental analyses undertaken during the challenge utilised trigger metrics from the TEMPER dataset only (see sections 3.3 and 4.2), the ten trigger metrics for this dataset have been listed below:

1. >75% of consent forms not returned by site
2. If death was reported, number of patients without the corresponding form
3. If progression was reported, number of patients without the corresponding form
4. Data Return threshold for poor performance, <70% with >30 CRFs outstanding, met twice in a row
5. >5 patients with last form received greater than 18 months ago
6. >5% of values in the open forms missing or queried
7. Total missing or queried values outstanding for >6 months
8. <10% of patients more than 6 months since Randomisation AND with at least 1 Serious Adverse Event (an event that risks patient safety, SAE)
9. >30% of patients more than 6 months since Randomisation AND with at least 1 SAE
10. General concern following review

Monitoring Reports

The monitoring reports contain action logs from in-person site visits during the periods matching those described above and these reports detail the issues found during the audit. These reports are available for both triggered and matched untriggered sites for the TEMPER study, but predominantly for triggered sites from the main study (due to visits being typically deemed necessary only for triggered sites). Each individual

issue found was graded as "Other", "Major", or "Critical" (in order of increasing severity) by the monitoring staff. Critical findings are specifically related to patient safety.

Each file consisted of 10 columns (key variables are marked *):

- Action ID - Unique numeric code of the finding and grade for a site
- Site ID - the unique numeric ID given to a site *
- Visit - The date when the visit to the site took place *
- Action - Whether the finding comment concerns something to do with the pharmacy, a general comment or a patient (among others)
- NA - If the Action concerns a patient, then the patient's ID is given
- DerivationCat - If the finding is related to a specific area e.g. screening of patients or problems with trial documentation it is noted here
- Finding - A string description of the finding *
- Grade - A categorical grade for the written finding *
- Completed action - The data at which the suggested course of action in the Finding was implemented
- Findings - A categorical variable describing whether a site has only Major/Critical findings or whether it has findings of all types *

A total of 666 and 1035 rows of data (for the main and TEMPER studies respectively) were supplied.

Post-Visit Performance Classification

Using the monitoring visit findings, each site was classified into one of three classes: 0 - no visit required, 1 - not usually visited and 2 - visit recommended. These classifications were set prior to the DSG in order to offer a ground truth, from which models could be trained.

Classes were set based on the number of issues found at the site and weighted for the severity grading of the issue (either 'Critical', 'Major' or 'Other') and cut offs for each class set so as to create a balanced training set within the TEMPER study data. Therefore for the TEMPER study, the data supplied included ten sites in each performance category. Two of the sites were visited on two separate occasions and these additional visits have been treated as separate data points in the initial basic analyses described in section 3.3.

For the main study, the data supplied included 2 sites at class 0, 14 sites at class 1 and 27 sites at class 2, skewed towards class 2 due to visits having been focused on sites that were deemed as requiring a monitoring visit.

3.2 Data issues

The multimodality of the dataset poses issues for integrating between the three data sources. This also means it can be difficult to apply certain machine learning techniques. In particular the CRF dataset contained responses to many questions from multiple different forms. This was complex to understand, in addition to this data consisting of different data types (e.g. text, numerical, multiple choice). The data recorded also changed over the course of the study, as forms evolved and were updated within the study protocol, for example where new questions were added or questions deemed not to add value to the study were removed. Pre-visit trigger data were also given as derived values from the CRF forms, and it was not possible to track back which specific CRF data these were derived from.

Further, findings from the monitoring reports do not necessarily correspond to specific forms or questions in the CRFs and pre-visit triggers, making these sources of information difficult to relate. In addition, clinical records use many acronyms and shorthand which led to difficulties in understanding of the data for those without clinical experience.

3.3 Exploratory data analysis

The TEMPER dataset was used for initial exploration. The analyses were performed using (i) the pre-visit trigger data that corresponded to the monitoring visit date and (ii) post-visit performance classification. Two analyses were performed, as described below. The data points in each figure within this section represent different sites.

1. Is there a relationship between the number of pre-visit triggers that fired for a site and its post-visit performance classification?

Figure 1: Number of triggers fired versus performance classification for each site

For each site, total number of triggers fired were plotted against performance classification (Number of triggers fired: range=0-6, mean=2.44) as shown in Figure 1. No significant difference in the number of pre-visit triggers that fired was found between performance classes ($F(2,29)=0.07$, $p=0.933$).

This finding confirms the urgency of developing improved techniques to determine which sites are most in need of a monitoring visit, with less than two triggers firing for half of the sites that were later confirmed as performing poorly (class 2, visit recommended).

2. Is there a relationship between the absolute pre-visit trigger values and post-visit performance classification?

For each site, absolute values were plotted against performance class, see figure 2. Where applicable, the currently used thresholds are indicated with a dotted line. Please note that triggers 8 and 9 use the same data but with thresholds of lower and upper limits respectively,

hence are displayed together on the same, lower right-hand plot. There appears to be some discriminatory potential for three of the current triggers: 'Data return when >30 CRFs Outstanding' (trigger no. 4), 'Progression Reported, No Form' (trigger no. 3) and 'Death reported, no form' (trigger no. 2), especially when considering discrimination of class 2 (visit recommended) sites.

A pair-wise comparison of pairs of absolute pre-visit trigger values was also undertaken. Figure 3 demonstrates how the increased number of progression forms not returned (trigger no. 3) for class 2 appears in combination with reduced data return rate (trigger no. 4), resulting in class 2 samples clustering above other samples (see top centre plot), demonstrating potential to improve discrimination of sites requiring a visit, simply by employing techniques that use combined absolute current trigger values, rather than the currently used method of separately assessing whether each trigger fired.

In conclusion, these exploratory analyses show that the current trigger method is not sensitive enough to determine the necessity of a monitoring site visit. Further, there appears to be little benefit in modifying the thresholds for each trigger, with the exception of trigger number 6 (values in the open forms missing or queried, where reducing this threshold below the current threshold of >5% may offer further discriminatory value (see Figure 2). Nevertheless, a combined trigger approach, using absolute values rather than threshold firing, may offer improved selection of sites requiring a visit over the currently used techniques. Hence to investigate this further, several different machine learning techniques were employed during the main part of the DSG challenge, as described below.

4 Experiments

This section describes the models developed during the DSG challenge, separated into two parts: (i) text-based approaches and (ii) numerical approaches.

For evaluation and comparison of models, the following performance metrics were employed:

Accuracy: The proportion of predictions correctly made by the model

Figure 2: Absolute values for each current trigger versus performance classification for each site, dotted lines represent currently used thresholds

Figure 3: Pairwise distribution of absolute trigger values by performance class. Axis labels refer to pre-visit trigger metrics as listed in section 3.1.

Confusion Matrix: Displaying the number of times instances of each true class are classified as each predicted class. Rows represent each true class and columns represent each predicted class. Diagonals therefore show the number of predictions that match the true labels

Where appropriate, further metrics have also been described for some models:

Precision: The proportion of positive classifications that are true positives

Recall (or Sensitivity): The proportion of true positives that have been correctly identified by the model

F1 score: F1 score is a harmonic mean of precision and recall, giving higher weight to lower values. A high F1 score is only achieved with high values of both recall and precision

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve: Sensitivity (true positive rate, recall) plotted against false positive rate

Area Under the Curve (AUC): Area under the ROC curve. A perfect classifier will have a ROC AUC equal to 1

4.1 Text-based Models

Text-based analysis techniques such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) are particularly useful for gaining insight from unstructured textual data, such as extracting semantic content from clinical data (Chen et al, 2020). The clinical trials datasets used for this study consisted predominantly of text data, both within the CRFs and the monitoring visit findings. Whilst the longer term aim is to develop a full monitoring system, with models relating monitoring findings back to pre-visit CRF data, due to the complexity of the CRF data and the time constraints of the DSG in developing pre-processing code for this complex dataset, the text-based models built during the DSG focussed solely on gaining deeper understanding of the monitoring finding data.

Several text-based models were developed, with the hypothesis that for each issue in the monitoring report, the grading assigned by trained monitoring team personnel ('Major', 'Critical' and 'Other') will be related to the words that appear in the issue description. Allowing for subjectivity between personnel regarding the grades assigned, for the most part, this hypothesis should hold true, given the training undertaken by monitoring

staff regarding how to grade monitoring issues.

This dataset offered an opportunity to investigate and categorise the vast array of monitoring issues found, using automated text-based techniques to guide the development of the full monitoring system. This initial work was necessary to allow deeper understanding of the typical issues found when undertaking a site visit and therefore provide insight into new metrics that could be measured from the pre-visit CRF data. For example, by fitting models to the written comments for each issue, analysis of the words associated with each grading could be undertaken.

NLP models were therefore developed during the DSG using both the 'Finding' and 'Grade' parameters within the monitoring visit report data. Whilst the grade is currently determined by trained trial monitors based upon the issue finding, NLP could reduce inherent subjectivity in this process. The 'Finding' parameter included a detailed free-text description of the issue found, providing further context for the 'Grade' parameter, which was set to either 'Critical', 'Major' or 'Other' by the monitoring team at the site visit. Five text-based methods were employed during the DSG challenge, as described below.

All text-based models were developed using the TEMPER study dataset unless otherwise described. For all models, the 'Finding' parameter was pre-processed by setting all characters to lowercase, tokenising each string into separate words and removing (i) words which lacked semantic meaning (such as 'the' and 'is'), (ii) punctuation and (iii) numbers.

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was performed with a deductive approach where coding and theme development were directed by the key categories of patient safety and informed consent. This was performed on the 56 'Major' issue examples and 3 'Critical' issue examples available within the TEMPER study monitoring report. The analysis uncovered three key themes within the data:

- (i) *Missing forms*: necessary forms for reporting consent or significant events are missing entirely from data (for form types: consent n=5, death n=3, progression n=1, SAE n=3, re-consent n=12)
- (ii) *Incorrect forms*: consent is not given according to trial standards, or SDV shows discrepancies (for form types: consent version n=10,

delayed/incomplete consent n=12, source-SDV discrepancy n=3)

(iii) *Patient safety*: significant measures impacting patient safety are not complete or fully investigated (for contraindication medication n=3, T status n=2, baseline measures incomplete n=4, toxicity n=1)

This analysis therefore indicates that ‘major’ or ‘critical’ issues found during monitoring visits are most commonly related to issues of correct consent completion and form return. This agrees with previous findings from the exploratory analysis of existing triggers, where triggers measuring data return and missing death and progression forms appeared to have the most discriminatory potential for selecting sites requiring monitoring visits. Evidence from this initial exploration suggests that there may be so far unexploited discriminatory potential using measures relating to missing consent forms and incomplete baseline measures and such measures could be used as new pre-visit trigger metrics.

Word Cloud

Monitoring finding data was grouped by finding grade (‘Critical’, ‘Major’, or ‘Other’) and represented as word clouds displaying the most frequently used words for each grade. For this analysis both the main study data and the TEMPER data were analysed as shown in Figure 4. For both datasets, data was skewed in favour of the ‘Other’ grade, particularly so for the TEMPER study data (where half of the sites would not have failed the pre-visit trigger metrics and not been routinely monitored in a clinical trial).

For the ‘Major’ grade issues found in the TEMPER study, (i) consent features highly through the words “consent” and “consented” and (ii) forms appear to be highlighted through the words “signed” and “version”. The ‘Other’ and ‘Critical’ grade issues from the TEMPER study featured words less common to running clinical trials, however it should be noted that the number of ‘Critical’ issues was incredibly low.

The ‘Major’ grade issues in the main study data featured the word “CAPA” which stands for Corrective and Preventative Action, for instance where immediate action is required to protect patients’ safety. Further, from the main study data, “Unreported” was a commonly popular word appearing within both ‘Major’ and ‘Critical’ grade issues sample sets.

Figure 4: Word clouds of text descriptions for each monitoring issue by grade ('Critical', 'Major', 'Other') for both the TEMPER data (top row) and the main study data (bottom row). Blanked out sections cover potentially sensitive trial information

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)

A topic modelling analysis was first performed using a Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model, an unsupervised machine learning technique. LDA models effectively reverse engineer documents, uncovering latent variables that govern the semantics of a document. The technique exposes the intra-document (as well as inter-document) statistical structure, by representing the document as random mixtures over latent topics, with each topic characterized by a distribution of words. For this dataset the maximum number of topics was set as 10.

Each word is then given a weighting value, based upon the number of times in other samples that the word has been assigned to that topic. The word is then assigned to the topic with the optimal weighting value. For this dataset, similar words appeared frequently and were assigned to different topics on repeat runs of the model, indicating that the model performance was poor for the small dataset available.

Topic coherence scores were then measured to assess the degree of semantic similarity between the words assigned within each topic and showed that reducing the number of topics created by the model resulted in an increase in coherence of words within each topic (see Figure 5). The dataset included a large number of repeated words. The ten most frequent words were: 'patient', 'consent', 'file', 'source', 'confirm', 'form', 'data', 'notes', 'week' and 'note', similar to the keywords observed with the other text-based model analyses.

TF-IDF and Multinomial Naive Bayes

Following the steps of instantiating, fitting and transforming the dataset for vectorization, the classic 'bag-of-words' (BoW) approach was used to undertake feature engineering to create suitable input for the Naïve Bayes classifier described below. Put simply, the model classifies text based on the probability of particular words within the text appearing for each class. Term Frequency Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), was employed due to its ability to measure the importance of words within text, to produce a feature matrix of the 'Finding' data. A Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier was then built, with a data split of 80:20 (train:test). This probabilistic classifier was used since it works well for classification using discrete features (such as word counts for text classification). The

Figure 5: UMass Coherence for number of LDA topics (coherence improves as UMass approaches zero)

multinomial distribution typically requires integer feature counts, but fractional counts like the output of TF-IDF were used here instead.

The Multinomial Naive Bayes model performed to an accuracy of 81%, with an AUC score of 0.86. These results indicate that this model type may be useful as a classifier of monitoring issue grade. The dataset was highly imbalanced, with the majority of samples being graded 'Other', and only a few samples with a 'critical' grading, therefore it would be expected that the model performed better for the grades with more samples ('Major' and 'Other'). This is reflected in the F1 scores obtained for the grades 'Critical', 'Major' and 'Other' were 0.0, 0.75 and 0.86 respectively. The confusion matrix (see Figure 6) displayed similar behaviour, with the model lacking any predictions of samples as 'Critical' grading. Larger datasets, particularly with a greater number of 'Critical' grade issue samples, would likely greatly improve the function of this classifier.

Bernoulli Naive Bayes

To further investigate which words described each different monitoring issue grade, a second Naive Bayes approach was implemented. Whilst 'critical' findings relate to patient safety and 'major' findings relate to the

scientific robustness of running the trial, both types of findings are considered of much greater significance than findings classed as 'other'. Due to the limited number of 'Critical' grade monitoring issues in the TEMPER dataset (n = 36), for this model, samples in these gradings were combined with 'Major' graded samples to create a model able to discriminate serious ('major' or 'critical' findings) from non-serious ('other' findings) issues. If more time had been available, a second model would have been created without such bucketing of data, i.e. keeping the finding grades separate as for the Multinomial Bayes model and a second Multinomial Bayes model also built replicating this bucketing method.

For the 'Other' graded issues, a precision of 0.75 and recall of 0.96 was achieved. For the combined 'Major' 'Critical' graded issues, a precision of 0.91 and recall of 0.58 was achieved. Figure 6 shows the confusion matrix for this model, indicating the model correctly identified 'Other' graded issues in the majority of cases, however tended to classify 'Major' and 'Critical' issues incorrectly as 'Other' graded issues for approximately 40% of the samples. Where 'Critical' issues correspond to patient safety and 'Major' issues relate to undertaking a trial in a scientifically robust manner, further investigation could help with understanding of whether the poor performance of this model arose due to the large differences between these grading types or due to large variation in issues found within each grading's sample set.

For each of the two sample groups ('Other' and combined 'Major' and 'Critical'), the ten words with the best predictive ability (using the highest log probability values) were then extracted from the model. Figure 7 shows a Venn diagram of the two sets of ten key words, with common words highlighted in the centre section. For the 'Major' and 'Critical' combined sample group, unique keywords to this grading were 'consent', 'form', 'trial' and 'provide'. For the 'Other' sample group, unique keywords were 'source', 'crf', 'data', 'within' and 'week'.

These findings add to understanding of those sites at a greater need for a monitoring visit, where issues with consent forms and at an overall trial level would be considered more significant, than issues regarding missing source and CRF data and may help guide development of new pre-visit trigger metrics in the future. Given the disadvantage that the Naïve Bayes

Figure 6: Confusion matrix output for TF-IDF and Multinomial Naive Bayes (Left) and Bernoulli Naive Bayes (Right) text-based models, built to predict monitoring issue grading from the issue description text

approach loses information on word dependence within samples, future work should also consider the use of NLP techniques capable of analysing complete phrases, to enable deeper understanding of the dataset and differences between issue gradings.

Summary

Both Multinomial and Bernoulli Naive Bayes classifiers demonstrated fair performance in classifying monitoring issue grade from the issue description alone. The availability of more data (preferably structured) is likely to further improve performance of these models, especially so for issues graded 'Major' and 'Critical', the primary grades of interest.

The thematic analysis, LDA, word clouds and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes classifier keywords highlighted how 'Major' and 'Critical' graded monitoring issues often involve issues with consent forms being missing or incomplete and indicates a key feature of clinical trials that would appear worth exploring in more detail, to uncover improved pre-visit trigger metrics.

**Top 10 predictive words
(log probability of feature given class)**

Figure 7: Venn diagram of top ten keywords extracted from the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes text-based model, built to predict monitoring issue grading from the issue description text

4.2 Numerical Methods

A suite of numerical models was developed to compare the ability of different machine learning techniques to predict the need for a site visit, using the pre-visit trigger metrics as described in section 3.1 that are currently used by the monitoring team.

Currently the standard practice is that the monitoring team select which sites will be visited from a list of sites that have two or more triggers fired. Models were initially built to predict need for a site visit using only binary values quantifying whether the trigger fired or not (i.e. whether the trigger value for that site met a given threshold or not, to mimic current practice). However, as to be expected, increased accuracy of models was later found when models were trained using the absolute values for each trigger.

The results presented here therefore represent models built using absolute values, with the ten trigger values for each site being input as a sequence of values. All numerical models were developed using the TEMPER study data unless otherwise specified. For the TEMPER data, trigger values were available from seven time points (calculated by the monitoring team approximately every three months), for each of the 30 sites. Site performance classification may have changed over the time period studied, however for the purposes of the DSG, for each site, trigger data from the different time points were labelled with the single performance classification available for that site. Where performance classification was calculated from the monitoring report data from that site (see section 3.1). This created a data set of 210 sets of trigger values with ground truth labelling. The ground truth labelling used was as described previously, a triple class classification, with labels 0 = no visit required, 1 = not usually visited, 2 = visit recommended. Models were trained with an 80/20 (train/test) data split, with accuracy measured using the test data set.

Logistic regression

Logistic regression (LR) is an easy to implement technique, used to predict categorical variables by implementation of a non-linear decision boundary. Here multinomial logistic regression was implemented, to classify site performance into one of three classes. This method demonstrated poor ability to predict the level of need for a site visit where

the accuracy of the model was only 0.36, precision just 0.39 and recall 0.43. The confusion matrix (see Figure 9) shows that few sites were classified as class '0' (no visit required) indicating that this model type overestimates the need for site visit. The ROC curve shown in Figure 10 further demonstrates the poor performance of this model. Whilst LRs are easy to implement they are prone to overfitting and tend to achieve poor accuracy with smaller datasets (Bailly et al. 2022), as demonstrated with the current application.

Support Vector Machine

Support vector machines (SVMs) employ hyper-planes (decision boundaries separating classes), setting a maximised margin between data from different classes. Improvements in performance can be achieved using kernel technology, transforming samples into an (infinitely) high dimensional space and facilitating improved decision boundaries, however this is at the expense of reduced interpretability of the model, a particular requirement for the application under study.

Limited time was available for automated hyper-parameter tuning, however using a manual technique the following hyper-parameters were optimal: gamma=5, C=4 and RBF kernel, the SVM model performed to a reasonable standard with the dataset employed, with accuracy of 0.64, precision of 0.65, and recall of: 0.66. The confusion matrix (see Figure 9) shows that fewer sites were classified as class '0' (no visit required) indicating that this model type overestimates the need for site visit. The ROC curve shown in Figure 10 further demonstrates the reasonable performance of this model.

These results demonstrate that given adequate tuning of hyper-parameters, this model type performs to a reasonable standard for this dataset.

Random forest

Random forest is an ensemble tree machine learning approach, using multiple individual decision trees to perform classification. Techniques such as 'bagging' (bootstrap aggregation, an ensemble learning technique) and 'feature randomness' (the generation of a random subset of features to ensure low correlation among decision trees) can be employed to reduce overfitting of the model, which is a common issue

with decision-tree approaches. Further, this technique offers a degree of interpretability using feature importance (by measuring how well the feature separates data at each node) and has the capability to achieve a fair level of accuracy with smaller samples of data particularly where classes are imbalanced in size (Bader-El-Den, 2019).

This model outperforms the other classification models built, with accuracy of 0.79, precision of 0.79 and recall of 0.82. The confusion matrix (see Figure 9) also demonstrates the superior performance of this model. The ROC curve shown in Figure 10 demonstrates comparable performance to other models for classes '0' and '1' and improved performance for class '2'.

Limited time was available for automated hyper-parameter tuning, however using a manual technique these results demonstrate that this model type performs to a reasonable standard for this dataset, where further tuning (for example with a grid search technique) may further increase performance.

XGBoost

The XGBoost model is an ensemble tree machine learning algorithm. The algorithm is based on the gradient boosting framework. Gradient boosting is a supervised learning algorithm that combines the estimates of a set of simpler, weaker models to predict the target variable. A key benefit of this method for this dataset is that the XGBoost algorithm works well with categorical variables and limited data.

Limited time was available for automated hyper-parameter tuning, however using a manual technique to optimise model accuracy, the following hyper-parameters were employed: a learning rate of 0.3, maximum depth of a tree of 6 and fraction of observations to be sampled for each tree of 0.9. Further tuning of hyper-parameters, such as using a grid search technique, may further improve the performance of the model.

The XGBoost model performed to a reasonable standard with the dataset employed, with accuracy of 0.69, precision of 0.69 and recall of 0.71. The confusion matrix (see Figure 9) shows a slight preference for this model to classify as class '0' (no visit required), in contrast to other models, indicating that this model type may underestimate the need for site visit. The ROC curve shown in Figure 10 further demonstrates the reasonable

Figure 8: Trigger Importance when classifying site performance, according to XGBoost model, where F score is a measure based upon the number of times the feature (or trigger, as labelled on the y axis) was used to split the data to predict site class

performance of this model.

These results demonstrate that given adequate tuning of hyper-parameters, this model type performs to a reasonable standard for this dataset (i.e. greater than twice the 0.33 accuracy achievable by chance for a three class problem), with relatively low computational demand (i.e. typically processing in under one minute)

A key benefit of XGBoost models is the ability to easily extract feature importance, in this sense describing the F Score, the number of times each feature (or trigger) was used to split the data in order to classify each site. Figure 8 displays the feature importance for the eight most important of the ten triggers, with trigger numbers 6 (values in the open forms missing or queried) and 8 (patients more than 6 months since Randomisation AND with at least 1 SAE) displaying the greatest importance.

Neural network

Neural networks typically function well only where large datasets are available (Bailly et al, 2022), with high risk of overfitting with lack of data availability during training. Nevertheless, with the potential for inclusion of data from other trials in the future, and advances in interpretability, this option was considered worth investigating as part of the DSG.

A fully-connected neural network model consisting of three hidden layers was built using Keras. The ten trigger values were passed through two dense layers consisting of 100 neurons, followed by a final layer that classified samples into one of the three classes, using the “softmax” function.

The neural network models developed during the DSG performed relatively poorly, as to be expected with the limited data available, with the optimal performance achieved from the model described above: accuracy of 0.48, precision of 0.51 and recall of 0.47. The models tended to over-fit, even with implementation of 20% dropout between each of the three layers. Whitening (rescaling the data to values between 0 and 1 using the ‘MinMax’ function) improved the performance for class ‘0’ samples (no visit required), but reduced performance for class ‘2’ samples (visit recommended).

Summary

Table 2 summarizes the results of the models described above. Due to the time restraints of the DSG, limited time was available to tune hyperparameters to achieve optimum results and was therefore limited to manual tuning. Automated tuning of hyperparameters would likely improve the level of accuracy that can be achieved, however there was not time to undertake this during the challenge.

Further, these results have been achieved with relatively small datasets, where the models that are more dependent on large datasets (e.g. neural network and logistic regression models) offered poorer performance, as would be expected.

Figure 9: Confusion matrix output for Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression models, built to predict site performance class from pre-visit trigger data

Figure 10: ROC curve output from the Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression (LR) models built to predict site performance class from pre-visit trigger data

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.79	0.79	0.82
XGBoost	0.69	0.69	0.71
SVM	0.64	0.65	0.66
Neural Network	0.48	0.51	0.47
Logistic Regression	0.36	0.39	0.43

Table 2: Summary of the classification models built to predict site performance class from pre-visit trigger data

5 Future work and research avenues

With the primary aim of this work being to explore novel pre-visit trigger metrics and improved prediction of clinical trial site performance prior to monitoring visits, the extensive work undertaken during the DSG has demonstrated several promising techniques that could be further developed to achieve this aim. In order to extend the text-based investigations, more sophisticated approaches to NLP could be used for information extraction, for example word embeddings such as Word2Vec or language models such as BERT, rather than the classic bag-of-words approaches used during the challenge.

Whilst the time available during the challenge did not permit models to be built with the complex and high-dimensional CRF data, the next step will be to relate the key topics uncovered during the DSG with the CRF data. An example of this is the prevalence for mention of consent forms in the outputs of the text-based models created, therefore extracting further information regarding their correct completion and date from the CRF data would appear worthwhile. Manual investigations of the CRF data during the DSG have revealed the following areas for suggested focused further exploration:

- Time delay between patient trial start date and consent form completion
- Number of measures missing at baseline (e.g. ECG, blood levels)
- Is re-consent required, and has this been undertaken?
- Failure of a clinical trial site to provide patient notes

A further consideration would be that a classifier could be more easily built using data from CRF forms containing only numeric data.

In order to better relate outputs of the text-based analysis of monitoring report findings with CRF data, a key method to explore further would be topic grouping within the CRF data, to explore matches with the topics found within the monitoring issue data. This approach may indicate which questions in the CRF data are instrumental in determining the likelihood of issues and poor performance at clinical trial sites.

Several numerical models have been developed during the challenge to classify clinical trial site performance. These models may be further improved by incorporating more sophisticated hyperparameter tuning such as grid search cross-validation. With the use of text-based models to uncover possible new pre-visit trigger metrics, their suitability for incorporation into the developed numerical classification models can easily be quantified by measuring improvement in model accuracy when the new metric is added. Achieving higher classification accuracy in such ways could lead to these classifiers being feasible for use clinically, predicting which sites would benefit the most from monitoring visits. Finally, it is recommended that by exploiting the metrics of feature importance that these models employ when classifying sites, further insight into how a site is underperforming could be achieved in future, explaining which areas the monitoring team would likely find issues in, should they choose to conduct a site visit.

5.1 Suggestions for Improvements to Available Datasets

A limitation of this research was the availability of sufficiently large balanced labelled datasets. Only the TEMPER data was balanced in its sampling (i.e. the dataset had an equal number of samples in each performance classification class), yet had only ten sites in each class. Improved accuracy of the numerical models would likely be achievable with a larger data set.

The high dimensional, complex layout of the CRF data made use of this data difficult within the time available. In order to relate this data to the monitoring findings, better understanding of the different forms that are completed during the course of the trial and separation of the data collected for each of these forms would be advised. Efficient use of this

data may also be aided by working alongside the monitoring team, in order that they can advise on which of the forms would likely relate more specifically to the monitoring findings. Further, future design of CRF forms may include specifically designed questions for upfront monitoring, for example questions focussed on the key terms mentioned within this report.

A common problem encountered when working with the data was string type variables containing spelling mistakes and irrelevant spaces. For example, in the CRF data, the QuestionName value "is form received" was spelled incorrectly in some instances (e.g. as "is form recieved"). Therefore future analysis of this data should incorporate the correction of spelling errors as a pre-processing step.

5.2 Summary

The output of the challenge has demonstrated the feasibility of improving current clinical trial monitoring by implementation of more sophisticated automated techniques than are currently used, for example by the use of machine learning models. This work could be invaluable in helping improve trial participant safety and the efficiency of clinical trials. This is increasingly important in light of the rapid clinical trial testing required during the COVID-19 pandemic, for both treatment and vaccine development.

With common issues occurring across different clinical trials, it would appear useful to determine a set of overarching triggers, that are common across trials and can be used to form a starting model that aids monitoring of different clinical trials. One such common issue is correct consent form completion, a vital step for all participants undertaking a clinical trial. This starting model could then be adapted for individual trials, with trial specific pre-visit trigger metrics used in addition to the common metrics, to personalise the model for each trial.

Finally, it would be suggested that such a model continues to learn iteratively, as the trial progresses, with implementation of techniques such as semi-supervised learning (i.e. the model learns from the outcome of ongoing monitoring visits throughout the trial) and learns how best to determine sites that are performing poorly, using data from the specific

clinical trial, whilst also improving the quality of monitoring information provided to the monitoring team. This could both aid efficiency when monitoring sites, by for example enabling the monitoring team to target the suspected issue during their site visit or even by eliminating the need for a full site visit entirely, if the suspected issue can be investigated remotely.

6 Team members

6.1 Participants

Aditi Dutta is a PhD student in Politics at the University of Exeter, Aditi is studying the dynamics of online misogyny through the use of both social science and natural language processing. She contributed to data pre-processing and the random forest classifier. Aditi also contributed to the NLP side of the project, building the LDA and Multinomial Naïve Bayes models, along with contributing to report writing.

Alden Conner is a Research Application Manager at the Alan Turing Institute. Alden works with Turing researchers to embed research outputs outside of the Turing and to support deployment of AI and data science tools to solve real-world problems. She supported the DSG group as a facilitator focused on project management and group organization.

Brandi Jess is a PhD student at Coventry University, Brandi's research focuses on modelling the thermal aspects of a car cabin. She was a participant in the challenge and contributed to the classification methods, particularly with pre-processing data, implementing XGBoost, and ensuring results were reproducible. She also contributed to the presentations and writing of the report.

Everlyn Kamau is a PhD student at the Nuffield Department of Medicine, Oxford University. Everlyn's research focuses on epidemiology and clinical surveillance of enteroviruses. Everlyn was a participant in the challenge and worked on logistic regression classification and writing the report.

Ifeanyi Chukwu is a data scientist in the Data Scientist Development Programme at Leeds Institute for Data Analytics, University of Leeds. Ifeanyi was a participant in the challenge and contributed to writing the NLP section of the report. Ifeanyi developed the word clouds, contributed to the exploratory data analysis and wrote the code for plotting the classification model findings (Confusion matrix and ROC curves).

Pingfan Song is a Senior Research Associate at the University of Cambridge, working on machine learning for healthcare. His research interests include machine learning, signal image processing with application to medical and biological imaging. Pingfan was a participant in the challenge and contributed to problem formulation, data visualization, programming and training of SVM and NN models and report writing.

Rebecca Woodrow is a PhD student at the University of Cambridge for Clinical Neurosciences. Rebecca worked on the exploratory data analysis for current triggers and monitoring reports, undertook the thematic analysis and provided expertise to the team regarding how clinical trials are run. She also contributed to report writing in particular describing the clinical problem and data, and future directions for the project.

Ross Laidlaw is a PhD student at the Universities of Edinburgh Glasgow studying precision medicine. Ross was involved in exploring the data feature space, helping team members understand the data, devising and writing code for the Bernoulli Naive Bayes NLP approach and identifying possible novel trigger features to explore in the data.

Sophia Batchelor is a PhD student at the University of Leeds and Centre for Immersive Technologies studying perception and sensorimotor learning in Virtual Reality environments. Sophia was a facilitator for the Data Study Group focused on project management and group organization. She also contributed to the initial NLP exploration and the writing of the report.

6.2 Principal Investigator

Louise Coutts is a Senior Research Associate at the Alan Turing Institute, working on the Statistical Machine Learning for Randomised Clinical Trials project. Louise has a PhD from the Institute of Cancer Research in medical physics and has several years postdoctoral experience developing machine learning models for healthcare and novel

clinical diagnostic imaging techniques. She helped preparing material for the challenge, provided background on current clinical trial monitoring techniques and explanation of the datasets provided to participants and collated and edited the final report.

6.3 Challenge Owners

Louise Brown is a Professor of Medical Statistics and Clinical Trials at the MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL. Louise joined the MRC CTU in 2012 and works mainly on cancer trials, particularly in stratified medicine. She focusses much of her time as the Project Lead for FOCUS4, a molecularly stratified adaptive trial programme in advanced colorectal cancer and STAMPEDE, a large adaptive clinical trial testing multiple treatments in advanced prostate cancer. She leads the statistical analysis for a number of stratified medicine projects in cancer including the SCORT and RE-IMAGINE MRC Stratified Medicine Consortia Programmes. She originally trained in mechanical engineering at the University of Manchester but after completing a Master's degree in medical statistics at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine she went on to complete her PhD in statistics at Imperial College London.

Carlos Diaz Montana is a Clinical Data Systems Manager at the MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL. Carlos has a MSc in Advanced Computing from the University of Bristol, and has several years of experience in software development and in designing and supporting computer systems for clinical research. One of his interests include methodology research in clinical trials conduct, in particular in trial monitoring and data management systems.

6.4 Project Team

Louise Coutts¹, Carlos Diaz Montana², Louise Brown², Sharon Love², Ian R. White², Chris Holmes¹, Karla Diaz Ordaz¹

1. The Alan Turing Institute, 2. MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL.

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turing.ac.uk
@turinginst